

DARIAH-EU

Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

ANNUAL REPORT 2017

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Foreword

Jacques Dubucs and Laurent Romary

2017 was a year of stabilisation for DARIAH. The organisation gained two new Directors, and reinforced its support staff with the addition of a Finance Officer. These two moves pointed toward a major shift in the DARIAH leadership, as well as an increasing recognition of our organisational maturity and changing needs as we have grown and consolidated our position. Indicative of this shift as well was the introduction of a more forward-looking culture, in particular through the introduction of the DARIAH Strategy Days and the development of the Strategic Action Plan.

From a scientific point of view, we have begun the process of developing the DARIAH Marketplace as a way of focussing our thinking about how DARIAH harnesses the power of its national contributors, exploring ways to turn their 'in-kind' contributions into a sort of 'out-kind' that can be highlighted and supported for reuse elsewhere. In addition, we have been able to focus on the increasing importance of the Working Groups, as reflective of the active communities of DARIAH. The number of WGs continued to grow in 2017, a process entirely motivated from the bottom up, and we have responded to this emerging strength by allocating funding to them for their activities.

Within our wider environment, we continued to ensure support and innovation through a strong EU agenda, including the finalisation of the Humanities at Scale project, which delivered signature programmes such as the Ambassador Network and the Regional Hubs. In addition, we worked together throughout the year in coordination with our sister Research Infrastructures within the PARTHENOS project on topics with a high shared value, and launched our DESIR project with its strong momentum towards building new communities and new countries.

Throughout all of these activities, 2017 has seen DARIAH become a mature institution with a widely recognised impact for accompanying the digital transition in the humanities. These activities are sure to bear fruit in the coming years, for DARIAH itself and for our wide community of researchers and collaborators.

Laurent Romary

President of the DARIAH Board of Directors 2017

Jacques Dubucs

Chair of the DARIAH General Assembly, 2017

Introduction

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) enhances and supports digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. DARIAH is a network of people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure that sustains researchers in building, analysing and interpreting digital resources. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level, enabling the transition to Open Science, and beyond to Open Innovation. It preserves, provides access to and disseminates research that stems from these collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed.

DARIAH was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in August 2014. Currently, DARIAH has 17 Members and many cooperating partners across 11 non-member countries.

DARIAH integrates digital arts and humanities research and activities from across Europe, enabling transnational and transdisciplinary approaches. In particular, it provides value to its members and stakeholders through the validation and sharing of data, services and tools; by providing training and education opportunities; by enabling 'bottom-up' organisation around emerging research needs; and through the exercise of foresight and policy engagement. Through these activities, DARIAH promotes the further development of research methods in the arts and humanities, documenting the state-of-the-art, supporting the preservation and curation of research data with a focus on particular challenges including diversity, provenance, multimedia collections and granularity, and acting as a coordinator and integrator for a diverse community of practice.

Structurally, DARIAH operates through the Europe-wide networks of the Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs) and their constituent Working Groups. Each of the four VCCs is cross-disciplinary, multi-institutional, international and centred on a specific area of expertise. VCC1, the e-Infrastructure, is responsible for DARIAH's technological foundations. It maintains a digital environment that allows community-developed data and tools to be shared and ensures the quality, permanence and growth of technical services for the arts and humanities. VCC2 is the Research and Education Liaison and acts as the primary interface with the research and teaching communities. VCC3 deals with Scholarly Content Management

in the various stages from creation, curation, and dissemination, through to the pooling of scholarly digital resources and results for reuse. VCC4 focusses on Advocacy, Impact and Outreach, interfacing with key influencers in and for the arts and humanities. Within this structure, DARIAH has over 20 dynamic Working Groups to integrate national services under specific operational categories.

DARIAH has impact on four interconnected domains: research, education, culture and economy. The consortium supports the sustainable development of digitally-enabled research in the arts and humanities by building services for researchers working with ICT-based methods. It helps them to further advance their research and ensures the long-term accessibility of their work, thus directly contributing to the understanding of the cultural, economical, social and political life in Europe and beyond. In addition, it offers teaching material as well as teaching opportunities to develop digital research skills.

DARIAH is at the forefront of a changing knowledge discovery market and possesses significant strength in this field through its partners. DARIAH also demonstrates how traditional humanities research skills play a prominent role in the digital age, and how such skills can be deployed in a digital economy setting. The DARIAH vision is that humanities researchers will be able to assess the impact of technology on their work in an informed manner, access the data, tools, services, knowledge and networks they need seamlessly and in contextually rich virtual and human environments and produce excellent, digitally-enabled scholarship that is reusable, visible and sustainable.

Activity highlights 2017

DARIAH Strategic Days: "Paving the way to translate ideas into actions"

The first edition of the DARIAH Strategic Days took place from January 12-13, 2017 at the Centre Marc Bloch, Berlin. Members of the DARIAH Senior Management Team, the Joint Research Committee and the DARIAH Coordination Office discussed and initiated a mechanism by which to plan action around key opportunities and threats for DARIAH, leading into the first version of the DARIAH STRategic Action PLan (STRAPL). For more information see page 24.

DARIAH Annual Event focused on "Sustainability" and DESIR Kick-off

The 2017 edition of the DARIAH Annual Event was held from April 26-27, 2017 at the Harnack House in Berlin. DARIAH Working Groups, researchers, DARIAH-related projects, and the DARIAH governing bodies met to exchange experiences, present progress, and discuss new ideas and future challenges around the topic of "Sustainability". The event also saw the starting event of the DESIR project, which will support DARIAH's expansion and consolidation. For more information see page 17.

For a better access to DH training: DARIAH and CLARIN relaunch the "Digital Humanities Course Registry"

Originally developed by DARIAH's Virtual Competence Center "Research and Education", the DH Course Registry, an online inventory of digital humanities modules, courses and programs in Europe, was relaunched during DARIAH's Annual Event in Berlin as a joint effort of the European research infrastructures CLARIN ERIC and DARIAH ERIC. For more information see page 22.

Cooperation Agreement between LIBER and DARIAH: "Advancing Digital Research is a Joint Effort"

Representatives of DARIAH and LIBER met in Lausanne, Switzerland, to sign a memorandum of understanding to define cornerstones for a closer cooperation with a main objective to promote the use of digital collections and digital techniques together.

LIBER is an association that represents more than 400 European libraries.

Speaking with one voice: DARIAH joins the ERIC Forum

In the frame of the 6th ERIC network meeting in Helsinki, DARIAH and other European Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) signed a Memorandum of Understanding establishing the "ERIC Forum". The forum formalizes the ERIC network meetings as a means to address common subjects which arise from the implementation of the ERIC Regulation by the European Commission. For more information see page 16.

New DARIAH Cooperating Partners

During its latest meeting, DARIAH's General Assembly accepted applications from seven universities and libraries from Bulgaria, Finland, Hungary, Norway and Romania to join the DARIAH Network as new Cooperating Partners.

Presenting European Digital Research in Canada: DARIAH contributes to DH 2017 in Montreal

DH 2017, the annual conference of the international Alliance of Digital Humanities Organisations (ADHO), took place in Montreal around the theme of Access/accès. Several members of the broader DARIAH community contributed actively to the conference by giving presentations on central aspects of DARIAH aiming to support emerging practices in the Digital Humanities.

Workshop: "Software Sustainability: Quality and Re-usability"

As part of ongoing efforts to align technology across the three Pan-European infrastructures for the Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities, representatives from CESSDA, CLARIN, and DARIAH held a workshop on "Software Sustainability: Quality and Re-usability", on 9-10 October in Berlin. Developers, users, service operators and IT managers presented work already accomplished as part of the tasks the infrastructures have undertaken in their efforts to become operational.

DARIAH Theme 2017: Cultural Heritage and Humanities Research

With a total of 66.090 Euro, seven projects were funded in the frame of the DARIAH Theme call 2017 on the topic of "Cultural Heritage and Humanities Research". A series of larger conferences, workshops and more interactive events such as hackathons were organised to examine relationships between researchers and cultural heritage institutions aiming to explore a variety of issues related to the expression of attribution and licenses, technical formats and recommendations for facilitating re-use, dissemination and hosting. For more information see page 21.

DARIAH Allocates Funds to Working Group Activities

In 2017 DARIAH successfully launched the first edition of the DARIAH Working Group funding scheme. With a total amount of 61.409 Euro, activities such as software and web development, the organisation of conferences, workshops and network meetings of 13 Working Groups have been supported in the areas of service development and scalability, sustainability, dissemination and growing DARIAH. For more information see pages 20-21.

I. Evolving and Involving

The DARIAH community in 2017

The nature of the DARIAH infrastructural community defies any attempt to simplistically quantify its size. Its effects ripple out from a small core staff to an ever widening community of individuals and institutions that organise themselves at both national and European levels. Furthermore, the nature of the DARIAH "user" tests the hierarchical dynamic implied by the term. Most DARIAH users are at the same time the creators of DARIAH, through their participation in Working Groups and projects, through their generation of in kind contributions and local influence.

The arts and humanities research base in Europe has been estimated to encompass more than 5 million individuals in research, teaching and cultural heritage. Every one of these is a potential DARIAH user, but the distributed nature of our organisation means that often, our 'touch' is at one or more degrees of separation from the central offices. That said, as we count the ripples flowing outward from our central

Hub, it quickly becomes easy to see how large our sphere of influence is. For example in 2017, DARIAH looked like this:

Each of these layers contributes to our unique strength, as the following examples from 2017 clearly illustrate.

Working Groups (WGs)

DARIAH Working Groups form the heart of the DARIAH community. They are grass-rooted, self-organised, collaborative groups which have their roots in existing communities of practice. As such, their structure is adaptable to changing needs or desires, and in response to these changing needs, new DARIAH Working Groups may be created to foster innovative scholarly practices and to provide the infrastructure to support them. In addition, existing Working Groups may develop and respond to changing circumstances by re-orienting their scope.

Figure 1: Size of the DARIAH Community, 2017

As of the close of 2017, DARIAH counted 21 Working Groups, which cover a wide spectrum of disciplines and collaborations between research and service institutions. Figure 2 visualises the current WGs and their assignment to Virtual Competency Centres.

In 2017, the Working Group **Training and Education** was split into two new Working Groups, each of which now focuses on particular goals and activities that evolved as two somewhat separate streams;

the Working Group **#dariahTeach** and the Working Group **DH Course Registry**. In addition, a new Working Group was initiated; **Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities (ELDAH)**. This Working Group will provide advice for all bodies in DARIAH on all issues related to privacy protection, intellectual property rights and ethical issues. It will also produce recommendations, as well as training and information materials related to areas of its expertise.

Founding the Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities (ELDAH) Working Group

The ELDAH WG, formed by Walter Scholger (University of Graz, Austria) and Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar (Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research, Croatia), initiate a discussion within DARIAH on issues related to five areas:

- Privacy and Confidentiality;
- Copyright;
- (Open) Licensing;
- Scholarly conduct (eg. in reviewing and publication); and
- Ethical issues generally.

The WG aims to develop an ethics and legal strategy which will inform researchers, providing guidelines and orientation for the conduct of their work, and contribute to better access to tools and data. Policy makers will equally profit from the outputs of the Working Group as they will be facilitated with background information on issues related to the Working Group's areas of concern.

Figure 2: Development of the DARIAH Working Groups, 2015-2017

DARIAH at the national level

This annual report focuses mainly on the activities of the DARIAH ERIC, also known as DARIAH-EU. But to see DARIAH through this lens only is to miss out on much of the activity that informs and shapes the overall force of DARIAH as a European research infrastructure.

National members of DARIAH meet each other and work together through the activities of the National Coordinators Committee (NCC). In 2017, this committee was very active, under the leadership of its new Chair and Vice-Chair, Toma Tasovac of Serbia and Sally Chambers of Belgium. In particular, the NCC collaborated to carry out an extensive comparative survey of national activities, the results of which pointed toward a number of potential initiatives for better engaging and aligning digital humanities research at the national level across Europe. One particular suggestion, which was quickly taken up, was the forming of transnational task forces within the NCC. In the course of the year, two such groups delivered position papers for consideration by the full NCC and the entire DARIAH community, one on the DARIAH Mission and one enumerating the benefits of DARIAH for member countries.

The NCC was also able to engage in outreach activities with the national representatives from the six candidate countries included in the DESIR project (see discussion on p. 12 below). Many of these candidate countries are already represented within DARIAH by institutions that participate as Cooperating Partners. In 2017, we welcomed 8 new partners in 6 different countries:

- Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" Sofia, Bulgaria;
- University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland;
- Central European University, Budapest, Hungary;
- Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary;
- National Library of Norway, Oslo, Norway;
- University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø, Norway;
- Babeş-Bolyai University, Transylvanian Digital Humanities Centre, Cluj, Romania;
- London School of Advanced Studies, United Kingdom

Denmark hosts DARIAH Innovation Forum

The DARIAH Innovation Forum was organised in the framework of our Humanities at Scale (HaS) project. In 2017 Aarhus was the European Capital of Culture, which offered a vibrant environment for cultural events, artistic interventions and performance productions, creative neighbourhoods and culinary venues for the DARIAH Innovation Forum. The Innovation Forum took place back-to-back with Creativity World Forum (Nov 1-2), the annual large-scale event for the global organisation Districts of Creativity. During this 3-day event, keynotes, workshops and a matchmaking event highlighted DARIAH's relations with traditional and digital industries.

The Innovation Forum strengthened and further explored cooperations of DARIAH and traditional industries associated with Arts and Humanities, like design and media, as well as new digital industries, like game development, social media, VR and AR, by bringing together researchers and the creative industries. Its program included a keynote by Prof. Andrew Perkis (of the Norwegian University of Science and Technology) on Arts and Technology, a presentation at the Aarhus Art Museum (AROS) of the new DARIAH Innovation Board, workshops on innovation in the digital transformation (Art, Humanities, GLAM, Creative Industries, Smart Environments), presentations of DARIAH services and projects, hosted at the Moesgaard Museum (Museum for Cultural Heritage, Archaeology, and Anthropology) and a matchmaking event for public-private partnerships in research and innovation. The matchmaking event was run in collaboration with Region Greater Denmark's Brussels Office, and targeted a number of upcoming European application calls for research and innovation, education and cultural creative collaboration.

Germany: official launch of the DARIAH-DE central office

During the DARIAH Annual Event 2017 which was hosted in Berlin, DARIAH-DE officially announced the opening of a central office in Göttingen and Tübingen. Since 2011, DARIAH-DE has been developing a digital infrastructure for humanities and cultural research in Germany with a total of 19 partners as a national sub-project of DARIAH ERIC, thanks to the support of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). The establishment of a central office has created an organisational framework that will enable DARIAH-DE to run sustainable operations on the long term.

"Stable digital research infrastructures are needed to support international and interdisciplinary research in the arts and humanities" said Dr. Klaus Schindel, Deputy Head of the Department "Humanities, Social and Cultural Sciences, Academies and Research Museums" of the BMBF. The office is located in the State and University Library Göttingen (SUB), which hosts the central coordination. The IT service company DAASI International in Tübingen ensures the technical operation of the research infrastructure. Together, they act as a central contact point for researchers and organisations on the arts and humanities disciplines in Germany. "With the founding of its office, DARIAH-DE has taken an important step toward the sustainability of the research infrastructure", explained SUB director and DARIAH-DE Consortium director Prof. Dr. med. Wolfram Horstmann. In addition to operating the digital research infrastructure on an administrative and technical level, the office promotes the further expansion and institutionalisation of DARIAH-DE.

Staying at the Cutting Edge

DARIAH's Scientific Board meets at least once annually to review DARIAH's activities, discuss its integration with wider trends in research and policy, and advise the DARIAH Board of Directors and General Assembly on strategy and overall direction for the ERIC. In 2017, the group met alongside the General Assembly and other DARIAH Committees in Aarhus, in a meeting that featured presentations by the SB members on issues related to the preservation and sharing of research data in the arts and humanities.

Board member Roxanne Wyns also gave one of the keynote lectures at the DARIAH Annual Event 2017 (a lecture which is available to watch on the DARIAH YouTube channel).

Roxanne Wyns

3 questions for Roxanne Wyns, member of the DARIAH Scientific Board

Roxanne Wyns works as innovation manager for LIBIS, a division of the Research and Development department of KU Leuven and part of the university library. Her area of expertise includes information solutions for managing, preserving and publishing digital heritage content as well as research applications for digital humanities research. She has been an active member of DARIAH Scientific Board since its creation in 2015.

How would you personally define the role of the Scientific Board?

The immediate answer would be advising the General Assembly and the Board of Directors on strategic issues. By doing that, a lot of questions arise: What DARIAH should be? Who should DARIAH represent? How can DARIAH bring added value for the research in humanities? How can DARIAH differentiate itself from the other European research infrastructures? I must admit that there are no straightforward answers. As part of the Scientific Board, I try to bring in my own experiences, knowledge and opinions on what I think a research infrastructure should be. The background of the Scientific Board members is very diverse and we all bring different areas of expertise. Because of my work experience, I focus primarily on technology. It took me some time to realise that DARIAH is more than a technical infrastructure; it is also a network of people, expertise, and knowledge. I have learned to appreciate that in DARIAH. I try to stay well informed on what is happening and give feedback on the documents I receive. I am very interested in the idea of a Marketplace that was introduced by Frank Fischer during our last Scientific Board meeting in Aarhus. I hope to see it come alive very soon. For me, the Marketplace should be a service catalog where people can find tools and services, but also dataset that is documented and interoperable. It should help project outcomes to be sustainable. If one thing is lacking in research, not only in the arts and humanities, it is well documented, interoperable datasets. And DARIAH can play an important role here; pass on the knowledge on how to model your data, how to map it to existing standards, how to document it properly so that someone else can reuse it. It is an important skill set, something that universities are challenged with and in which DARIAH can take on an important role for humanities.

You were invited to give a lecture during the DARIAH Annual Event 2017 on challenges and opportunities of digital research. What was the message you wanted to deliver to the communities?

The focus of the DARIAH Annual Event 2017 was on sustainable research infrastructure. As you may have noticed, it is an important topic for me. I work as innovation manager at LIBIS and I collaborate extensively with research groups and partners from the cultural sector. What I noticed is that they have ideas, then funding, to build tools, services or databases, but they never think of the long term: what happens once the funding stops? Infrastructure projects, being hardware, software or even the human interaction parts behind them, keep costing money after the end of the project. Through the Annual Event 2017, DARIAH had the ambition to inform its communities about the challenges of sustainability. The awareness is growing but slowly. DARIAH has an important role to play by providing a framework for best practices in sustainability: how to share, how to document data.

On a different note, what I really appreciated during the Annual Event was interacting with the Working Groups and the communities. The Scientific Board members usually meet during the General Assembly and we don't really get to know the various communities in DARIAH. Going to the Annual Event helped me better understand the needs and ambitions of the researcher, how they see their futures and how they think DARIAH can play a role in that.

How do you picture DARIAH in the near future, which direction should it take?

I have been in the Scientific Board for the last 3 years. At the very beginning, DARIAH seemed pretty chaotic and difficult for us to understand. But in the past year, it has become a lot more mature; reflecting clearly about its strategy and its position in the research landscape. I think it helps DARIAH to understand what is important, in which projects it should be involved. The strategic action plan is a useful tool in order to set up the strategic goals and evaluate DARIAH's participation in projects according to objective criteria. What I will like to see in the coming years is the further development of formalism that is now taking place. You always need freedom to be innovative but as an organisation grows, you need more formal structure, rules and procedures.

Furthermore, I think that the Marketplace will play a key role for DARIAH, something that will allow DARIAH to differentiate itself from the other research infrastructures. More and more research infrastructures in the humanities will be created in the near future. And I wonder if they will all thrive or fight for the same amount of funding. If DARIAH wants to keep an important role and attract more partners, it needs to have a value proposition towards its communities. And I think the Marketplace can be that.

The DESIR Project

The DESIR (DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined) project launched in January 2017 with the purpose of strengthening the sustainability of DARIAH and firmly establishing it as an essential leader and partner within arts and humanities communities for the long term. The project addresses three main challenge areas: organisational capacity, member engagement and network expansion, including aspects of dissemination, growth, technology, robustness, trust and education.

Over the course of 2017, the DESIR team began the process of supporting the maturation of new DARIAH member countries, in particular Finland, United Kingdom, Czech Republic, Spain, Switzerland and Israel. The first year of the project saw each of these countries developing the research roadmap and networks required to propose eventual membership. DESIR also began preparing for a series of events to take place in 2018 called "DARIAH beyond Europe," high-level international events in the US and Australia with partners in Stanford University, the Library of Congress and the Australian National Data Service (ANDS, now the Australian Research Data Commons).

DESIR also began to develop new services for DARIAH in 2017, including entity-based search, scholarly content management, text analysis services and visualisation. In order to define requirements for these services, a gap analysis of the current DARIAH infrastructure was conducted, and a workshop, entitled "Software Sustainability: Quality and Re-usability" was held in October 2017, bringing DARIAH representatives together with other research infrastructures such as CLARIN and CESSDA. One key lesson learned from the event was the need to define quality measures and criteria for the operation of infrastructure services. These achievements are only the start for DESIR, however: the project will also reinforce DARIAH governance with robust business planning, the implementation of a helpdesk, an assessment of impact in new communities, development of strategies to increase trust and confidence and also training activities in new countries.

Ambassadors Network

Another project-led initiative that contributed to the DARIAH community in 2017 was the formation of an Ambassadors Network within the project Humanities at Scale (HaS). The Ambassadors network was designed to engage key individuals within regions or communities of practice with less exposure to DARIAH, empowering them to be able to speak about and for DARIAH. A call for proposals was published in March 2017 and six ambassadors were appointed. Each of them implemented an individual project to raise awareness of and participation in DARIAH across the emerging regions, marginal communities and new disciplines in what

is currently conceived of as the digital humanities. Beneath this umbrella they covered a broad range geographically and intellectually, from Sarajevo to Trondheim and from library science to natural history. The programme led to greatly increased awareness of DARIAH in these key emerging communities, and exposed more than 650 new researchers and policymakers to DARIAH's activities. To learn more about what an Ambassador's experience was like, see the text box below.

Claire Clivaz, DARIAH Ambassador

Claire Clivaz, leader of the Digital Humanities+ group at the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, was one of our DARIAH Ambassadors. Claire's project was inspired by needs she saw in her own networks, but also by the experiences of Switzerland as a DESIR candidate country.

In the course of her project, she not only organised a workshop for her local community in Zurich, but also took part in DARIAH events in Poland and Romania, and represented DARIAH at conferences in Montreal, Canada and Krasnoyarsk, Russia. She also used some of her Ambassador funding to support six young researchers to attend the events in Russia and Romania, where she co-organised DARIAH-workshops.

Of her experiences, Claire says that *"The Ambassador grant was absolutely successful to engage a new public, in particular the two calls addressed in Russia and Romania, and the Zurich workshop. The grants were a way to show concretely how DARIAH can provide support to scholars still not related to the ERIC."*

Regional hubs

DARIAH has been very successful in its mission to expand via the addition of new member states, but recognises that it also needs to further expand to increase its presence in European countries that do not yet have a strong researcher base in the digital arts and humanities, or which are not yet members of DARIAH. To this end, within the Horizon 2020 project Humanities at Scale, four different regional hubs were developed in 2017, each with the goal of consolidating activity and knowledge across national borders. The hubs were formed around two specific objectives: to build national consortia and explore possibilities for joining DARIAH and to meet specific needs relevant within local and regional communities. Throughout the hubs, many successful thematic events have been

organised, such as "EpiDoc", a training workshop for digital editing of epigraphic and papyrological texts. The four hubs included: DARIAH-GR acting as a hub for Romania and Bulgaria, DARIAH-HR for the Western Balkans, DARIAH-EU in cooperation with Austrian and Hungarian partners explored the possibility of a Central Europe Hub, DARIAH-DK set up a Nordic Hub covering Nordic countries while DARIAH Benelux emerged as well. The contribution to DARIAH via these hubs has been significant, as several Universities and research centres from the targeted countries later joined DARIAH as cooperating partners and the initiatives triggered collaboration between communities and institutions on the transnational level.

DARIAH NORDIC HUB

A shining example is given by the Nordic Hub, coordinated by Marianne Ping Huang. Initiated in fall 2016, it connected DARIAH-DK with Nordic collaborating institutional members: University of Helsinki, Linnaeus University and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology. The objectives were to map Nordic common interests in research and education in Digital Humanities and the digital transformation of Arts and Humanities, addressing future projects and collaboration and sharing knowledge on national membership and application processes. As a result, a common application was submitted to Nordforsk, an organisation under the Nordic Council of Ministers that facilitates and provides funding for Nordic cooperation in research. The objective of the application was to form a Nordic University Hub addressing the digital transformation of Humanities research, education, knowledge sharing and capacity for open innovation. Although the NordForsk application was not successful, collaboration within the DARIAH Nordic Hub continues along these lines. The Nordic Hub has a strong focus on education and was represented at the annual DH Nordic pre-conference workshop on digital transformation of humanities education.

Reaching out: DARIAH Collaborations Across Boundaries

DARIAH's embedding into its environment of similar and distinct organisations made significant progress in 2017, as our growing confidence of our mission and identity made us able to reach out across boundaries to engage as leading partners in strong and mutually beneficial bilateral and group initiatives. This has taken place on many levels:

Locally

In particular when it comes to creating event-based opportunities for learning and knowledge sharing, DARIAH works with local and discipline-based partners to achieve the best possible awareness of and participation by target groups. One example from 2017 was the digital lexicography masterclass (described on page 19 below) which DARIAH co-organised with the Centre Marc Bloch, the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences (BBAW), Inria (Paris, France) and the Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities (BCDH, Serbia). The event was further supported by the German Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), CLARIN, DARIAH-DE and the H2020 European project "Humanities at Scale". While it may not be always the easiest to bring together such a broad consortium for an event, the eventual success is compelling evidence for the value of the effort.

The Data Reuse Charter

The Data Reuse Charter began as a DARIAH initiative to promote communications around the conditions for reuse of the kinds of data that humanists generally deal with in their research: cultural and historical documents. In particular as expectations increase that researchers will be able to openly share their research data and source material, the lack of clarity and huge divergence in practices around the conditions for reuse of sources is emerging as both a barrier and a potential threat to the future development of humanities research. In response to this, DARIAH instigated a series of meetings between key stakeholders to share knowledge and devise methods by which the goal of enhanced data fluidity can be achieved. The Charter Task force included CLARIN, Europeana, Archives Portal Europe, the ARIADNE Project, E-RIHs and the PARTHENOS RI Cluster. Although it will take many more years to truly tackle the issues the group faced, it can already count among its outputs an award-winning poster

THE DATA REUSE CHARTER POSTER

presented by Anne Baillot at the DHd 2017 conference on "Digitale Nachhaltigkeit", which took place in Bern (Switzerland) from 13th to 17th February 2017.

The European Association for Social Sciences and Humanities: EASSH

Towards the end of the year, DARIAH also began collaborating with the European Association for Social Sciences and Humanities. The 'European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities' (EASSH) brings together scientific networks, associations, disciplines and universities. The main purpose of EASSH is to promote research on social sciences and humanities as a resource for Europe and the world, to which end they act as channel to and from the social sciences and humanities to the research system of civil society, policy makers, advisors, public-private partnerships, administrators and practitioners. In particular, the broad base of members and policy and lobbying focus of EASSH provides a potentially strong complementarity that we look forward to developing.

LAUNCH OF THE DARIAH-CLARIN COURSE REGISTRY AT THE DARIAH ANNUAL EVENT 2017 BY LAURENT ROMARY, FRANK FISCHER, JENNIFER EDMOND, MATEJ DURCO, WALTER SCHOLGER, HENDRIK SCHMEER AND DARIA FIŠER

PARTICIPATION OF DARIAH AT THE ERIC FORUM, MAY 2017

CLARIN-ERIC

In the course of 2017, DARIAH has begun a very promising series of meetings and collaborations with the CLARIN ERIC. Although constituted under the same instrument of a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, CLARIN and DARIAH have very different structures, user models and research communities, and yet the overlaps make a very productive basis for collaboration and cooperation. In particular, DARIAH and CLARIN have moved forward with the shared revision and release of the (formerly DARIAH, now DARIAH-CLARIN) course registry, described in more detail on page 22). By working together, we were able not only to update and improve the technical infrastructure, but also build the content in the course registry to reflect related fields and courses.

The ERIC Forum

As an European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), DARIAH is involved in the ERIC network, which organises twice yearly meetings of members from across the research infrastructure landscape. These meetings give the ERICs from across the disciplines and across Europe an opportunity to share best practices and hold workshops on topics of shared, transversal interest among its members. In May of 2017, the informal grouping of the ERICs that had been meeting took the step of constituting itself as a formal organisation, the ERIC Forum. Constituted by the ERICs from all disciplines, the Forum is dedicated to promoting all forms of knowledge exchange about the organisation, structuring and policy issues and the impact upon ERICs. In particular, issues such as impact assessment, human resourcing, financial administration and links to initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud have been featured in their discussions. DARIAH was glad to have the chance to be a founding member of the ERIC Forum, and will look forward to using it as a mechanism to ensure we remain at the cutting edge of best practice in how we manage and maintain our activities.

II. The Maker and the Explorer

Fostering Excellence and Building Capacity Across the Divide Between Basic and Applied Research

Infrastructure in the arts and humanities is generally most effective when it is deployed tactically: that is, at a level of scale and complexity that can encompass the breadth of disciplines and methodologies an organisation like DARIAH represents. For this reason, we place a lot of importance on:

Events

Bringing people together to share knowledge and develop a common skills base is one of the most important things DARIAH does. In 2017, we hosted and supported a very wide range of events, as the following descriptions will show.

Annual Event 2017

On 26 and 27 of April, the DARIAH Annual Event 2017 gathers 162 members of the DARIAH Community at the Harnack Haus in Berlin. The diverse program inspired the exchange of experiences, both substantive and organisational, as well as the conceptualization of innovative plans for the future, around the central theme of 'sustainability.'

In the plenary part of the program, two keynote speakers were featured. Prof. Dr. Isabella Peters spoke about open science and libraries in her lecture "Keep calm and yes, we're open today", and Dr. Roxanne Wyns discussed the challenges and opportunities of digital research in her lecture "From paper to digits". In addition, the DARIAH directors commented on their vision on the DARIAH strategy 2020 in a Q&A session, and the DARIAH related projects HaS, DESIR, HIRMEOS, PARTHENOS and E-RIHS were discussed in a plenary panel session.

The programme also facilitated a large number of Working Group Meetings, providing them with a platform to meet their groups face-to-face and to share knowledge with other WGs. Across the spectrum, the DARIAH WGs seized the opportunity to present progress and new ideas to the wider public, and discuss future challenges.

The second day of the event was kicked off with a lively dialogue during the Marketplace poster session. The Marketplace was followed by a break-out session in two workshops: "The Research Data Alliance (RDA) and sustainable research data sharing", organised by RDA, and "Sustainability of Digital Research Infrastructures for the Arts and Humanities" organised by the German CLARIN-D and DARIAH-DE (see textbox).

CLARIN-D and DARIAH-DE Workshop at the DARIAH Annual Event

One of the workshops at the Annual Event was co-organised by CLARIN-D and DARIAH-DE, the German national instantiations of the DARIAH ERIC and the CLARIN ERIC. Both initiatives support diverse research projects and develop the tools and services according to the needs of the varying communities in these fields with different foci. This results in different infrastructure components, but, where possible, a close collaboration in technical and organisational matters.

At this workshop these two initiatives shared their experience in seeking sustainability on a national level, and discussed challenges in maintaining digital research infrastructures centered around issues such as: what organisational models best promote sustainability, ideal and feasible funding models, international cooperation as a driver for sustainability, researcher requirements and communities, and different aspects of sustainability.

In three presentations, strategies for sustainability were presented from a national and a European perspective, as well as from the Digital Humanities Community perspective. After these introductions, the audience was invited to participate in the discussion and pose questions to the panel of presenters constituted by Evelyn Gius (Association for Digital Humanities in the German speaking area (DHd)), Laurent Romary (DARIAH-EU), Erhard Hinrichs and Andreas Witt (CLARIN-D), Wolfram Horstmann (DARIAH-DE) and Stefan Schmunk (chair). The workshop was attended by some 50 people from across the DARIAH communities. The discussions held gave birth to the idea of organising a workshop series on Research Infrastructures for the Humanities which will aim to gather the requirements from various disciplines to be considered by the German research funders, particularly the Federal level and the states for a sustainable national research infrastructure.

DARIAH TRAINING SCHOOL HOSTED BY THE CHARLES UNIVERSITY PRAGUE AND CNRS, HAS PROJECT

Training Schools

Lexical data masterclass

The aim of the DARIAH lexical data masterclass was to bring trainees and experts together in order to share experiences, methods and techniques for the creation, management and use of digital lexical data. The 20 participants were mentored by 7 tutors who introduced specific methods during instructional sessions that have been used during the masterclass. Among the tutors were core DARIAH contributors, such as President of the Board of Directors Laurent Romary and NCC Chairperson Toma Tasovac, as well as local and international scholars from Germany, France, the Netherlands and the United States.

A specific outcome of this masterclass, conceived as a set of training and working sessions where most of the knowledge transfer is issued through the concrete work on the participants' projects, was contribution to the assessment of the standardization landscape, in particular the TEI guidelines. Besides,

the importance of providing more awareness to data management issue was highlighted during the week, as well as the need to increase the amount of openly available resources.

The masterclass contributed to both CLARIN and DARIAH's strategic commitment to training and education as an essential component of infrastructure building. The discussions of various data formats, standards and general data management practices in the lexical domain helped attendees expand their horizons and adopt new skills, and the training resources are now available for reuse in a GitHub repository. The success of the event was such that the "Lexical Resources" Working Group plans to continue developing the model, a fruitful cooperation between CLARIN and DARIAH in this field may continue in the future as well.

Humanities at Scale Summer Schools

The EC-funded Humanities at Scale project sponsored two training schools in the course of 2017 in order to encourage the uptake of the of the DARIAH infrastructure, education and training activities. In July, an event called "Bibliotheca Digitalis – Reconstitution of Early Modern Cultural Networks: From primary source to data" was organised in Le Mans. It provided introductory training in the application of digital methods to Early Modern Historical documents and was attended, after a competitive call for participation, by 20 scholars from all over Europe. In September, the Summer School "Beyond Editing: Advanced Solutions and Technologies (BEAST)" took place in Prague and was dedicated to TEI encoding. 21 applicants from 11 different countries were selected. The event has been organised with the collaboration of the Charles University Prague and CNRS.

"The Summer school was a great experience. Teachers were fantastically nice and all leaders in their field. The idea to mix IT specialists and humanists, both working together, was excellent. Meeting fellow participants was also great, since they were coming from different countries and background: researchers or librarians, more or less advanced, from France, Italy, Canada, Hungary, etc. It was a great opportunity to exchange about possible collaborations, learn new things and, above all, share a good moment together." Simon Gabay, University of Neuchâtel, participant at the "Bibliotheca Digitalis – Reconstruction of Early Modern Cultural Networks: From primary source to data" in Le Mans, July 2017.

JENNIFER EDMOND DEVELOPED A STRATEGY UNIT, IN COLLABORATION WITH THE RITRAIN TEAM AT THE UNIVERSITY OF MILAN BICOCCA

European Masters in the Management of Research Infrastructures (EMMRI) Unit on Strategy

In addition to our sustained commitment to supporting humanists in the development of the digital skills, DARIAH also participated in 2017 in the development of a unique training experience for research infrastructure management professionals. Within the RITrain programme, students pursue an executive Masters programme designed to help them to face the unique challenges of managing large, distributed research organisations like ERICs. DARIAH Director Jennifer Edmond worked with the RITrain team based at the University of Milan Bicocca to develop a unit on strategic planning, based on DARIAH's own experiences with the Strategic Action Plan.

Funding Schemes

Each year, DARIAH distributes funding within its network in order to create a coordinated body of activity around key themes, to support strategic development, and to incentivise further collaboration with and within the DARIAH network. In 2017, we ran two such schemes, one to pursue thematic work related to cultural heritage and humanities research, and one to support the ever-more central contributions of our Working Groups.

The DARIAH Theme 2016-17: Public Humanities

Throughout 2017, the DARIAH community was offered a wide variety of opportunities to think about the impact of DARIAH's work on the general public or specific organisations such as media or educational institutions, for example schools.

The activities and events delivered in 2017 included workshops on:

- "Open Education. The Why and How of Digitally Enhanced Learning for Communities of Enablers," an exploration of digital pedagogy delivered by the #dariahTeach team.
- "Digitisation of Heritage Librarian Funds: Our Necessity and Obligation" an initiative of DARIAH-HR
- A "Public History Bootcamp" to raise awareness of both digital humanities and public history methods (DARIAH-IE)
- "MediaDNA – Investigating emerging technologies in Humanities research to serve public use of digitised audio-visual material" exploring the potential of video recognition, fingerprinting and data tracing technologies within the Digital Humanities (DARIAH-NL) and
- "Public humanities and digital humanities: mutual inspiration and common (digital) tools," which brought together scientific institutions and GLAM institutions involved in public humanities (DARIAH-PL).

Many of the projects were presented through a poster slam session in November 2017 in Aarhus.

The DARIAH Theme 2017-18: Cultural Heritage and Humanities Research

The aim of the DARIAH Theme 2017-18 was to bring cultural heritage institutions and researchers together in order to explore a variety of issues related to the expression of attribution and licenses, technical formats and recommendations for facilitating re-use, dissemination and hosting. The call for proposal specifically encouraged contributions to the Data Re-Use Charter project, but remained open as well to other approaches on how to identify which rights apply to the sources researchers are working with, in terms of use and above all re-use when they intend to publish results based on these assets. On this basis, seven projects were awarded a total of almost €70,000 for their initiatives.

The results are supposed to be presented at the DARIAH Annual Event 2019 in Warsaw.

WG Funding Scheme 2017

The Working Groups in DARIAH are a self-organised, grass-rooted mechanism to collaborate on certain issues across national and institutional boundaries. In 2017, however, DARIAH launched a funding stream to support the efforts of the Working Groups, and strengthen their role and effectiveness. The scheme was designed to offer practical support for their programmes, encouraging Working Groups to put forward innovative ideas, run pilot programmes, and build up capacity to suggest new services or help develop and sustain existing ones.

Overall, 13 projects successfully secured funding for a broad variety of projects, all to take place between 1 November 2017 and 31 October 2018. While the true outcomes of the scheme will only be seen coming into fruition over the course of 2018, what is already clear, however, is the extent to which the scheme has been able to get WGs to think of their impact and activities on a different scale, and expand the access to them.

From the WG Community Engagement

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT
DARIAH - EU VCC2 WORKING GROUP

"Working Groups are a vibrant part of the DARIAH structure. Allowing them to claim support and funding within DARIAH to shape their own research agenda, be more motivated to develop, have a stronger presence and voice in meetings, conferences and events across the field, and address some of the major areas of 'DARIAH 25 of 2020' strategy goals is absolutely beneficial and vital for sustaining and enhancing their role within the network."

Tools and Platforms

Although DARIAH and its community benefits greatly from interactions within small groups and at face-to-face events, as a virtual research infrastructure, we also interact increasingly through more generic services and platforms, which DARIAH is uniquely able to provide. 2017 saw the release of two major such initiatives, which DARIAH will sustain as central services for its community.

Course Registry

The **CLARIN/DARIAH DH Course Registry** offers a map-based search environment that gives access to a database that contains information on Digital Humanities courses offered by European academic organisations. The goal of the DH Course Registry is to provide information to: (i) students and researchers who intend to take up a study in the field of Digital Humanities, (ii) lecturers who are looking for examples of good practices in the DH field or want to promote their own DH-related teaching activities and material, and (iii) administrators who aim to attract and facilitate international student and staff mobility and exchange. Although it was initially developed some years ago as an initiative of DARIAH's VCC 2, the 2017 release brings both a new level of heightened technical robustness, user tuning, and the strong cooperation of CLARIN and DARIAH to its sustainable growth and development.

DIGITAL HUMANITIES COURSE REGISTRY

Search Options:

- Country: [dropdown]
- City: [dropdown]
- Institution: [dropdown]
- Education: [dropdown]
- Disciplines: none selected
- Techniques: none selected
- Objects: none selected

Status	Course Name	Education Type	Institution	Department
Full time course 2018-21-01	Informatica umanistica	Degree: Master Programme	Università degli studi "Gabriele d'Annunzio"	Dipartimento di Scienze Filosofiche, Pedagogiche ed Economico-Quantitative
Full time course 2018-01-01	MA in Digital Art History/Computational Media	Degree: Master Programme	Duke University	Art, Art History & Visual Studies
Full time course 2018-01-01	Suonois Digital Classics	Degree: Master Programme	Universität Leipzig	Institut für Informatik
Full time course 2018-01-01	Double licence Lettres - Informatique	Degree: Bachelor Programme	Université Paris-Sorbonne	UFR Littérature française et comparée
Full time course 2018-01-01	Heritage Visualisation	Degree: Master Programme	The Glasgow School of Art	School of Simulation and Visualisation
Full time course 2018-01-01	Master Humanités numériques	Degree: Master Programme	Université Lyon 2	ICOM
Full time course 2018-01-01	Introduction aux Humanités Numériques	Credits: Course	Le Mans Université	Département d'allemand
Full time course 2018-01-01	Pratiques numériques dans l'enseignement en France et en Allemagne	Credits: Course	Le Mans Université	Département d'allemand
Full time course 2018-01-01	Urheberrecht im europäischen digitalen Raum	Credits: Course	Le Mans Université	Département d'allemand
Full time course 2018-01-01	Comprendre et utiliser les bases de données	Credits: Course	Le Mans Université	Département d'allemand
Full time course 2018-01-01	Introduction à la Traduction Automatique	Credits: Course	Le Mans Université	Département d'allemand
Full time course 2018-01-01	Programming for Digital Humanities	Credits: Course	Linnéuniversitetet	Institute; Department of Computer Science and Media Technology
Full time course 2018-01-01	Game studies	Credits: Module	Universiteit Utrecht	Arts

The OpenMethods metablog: Leveraging on the power of expert content curation

OpenMethods, a metablog for the sharing of scholarly communications material, was created through the Humanities at Scale project with the goals of broadening and deepening the adoption of digital tools and methods and facilitate the culture of reuse of already existing resources. Enabling content curation and helping researchers to stay on the top of the enormous amount of literature available online was also a key priority. The platform focuses and stimulates discussion on DH research methods and tools. Such a discourse is

especially important in the increasingly data-driven and computationally sophisticated landscape of humanities. It also brings together a number of DARIAH-developed (such as the semantic standard TaDiRAH) and new or adapted components to create a unique, multilingual environment for scholarly communications in the humanities, enabling heightened visibility and peer recognition for a wide variety of content types like blog posts, videos, presentations, or podcasts and grey literature.

The screenshot shows the OpenMethods website interface. At the top, it features the logos for 'Humanities at Scale' and 'DARIAH-EU' above the main title 'OPENMETHODS' and the subtitle 'HIGHLIGHTING DIGITAL HUMANITIES METHODS AND TOOLS'. A navigation menu includes links for HOME, ABOUT, WHO WE ARE, JOIN US, SUBMIT A CONTENT, RSS FEEDS, and LOG IN. The main content area is divided into three columns. The left column features a featured article titled 'Not All Character N-grams Are Created Equal: A Study in Authorship Attribution - ACL Anthology' with an introduction and a 'READ MORE' button. The middle column displays a grid of 'Stranger Things' character images and a featured article titled 'It's personal, isn't it? What personalization means for internet research methods - AoIR' with an introduction and a 'READ MORE' button. The right column contains a search bar, a 'CATEGORIES' dropdown menu, and a 'RECENT POSTS' section listing the two featured articles.

III. “Doing things right ... and doing the right things”

Becoming a more efficient, strategy-led organisation

2017 will be remembered in DARIAH as a moment when we began to move from a responsive and reactive mode of development to a strategic one. DARIAH's first ever 'Strategy Days' were held in January of the year, bringing together the Strategic Management Team and the Joint Research Committee to take a high-level view of DARIAH's activities, 'Dreaming our DARIAH' but also assessing the manner in which key documents, such as our mission statement and high level principles, did or did not capture the value we felt the organisation needed to bring. This move was inspired on the one side by the maturity we had gained: after 10 years of growth and development, the organisation had formed an innate sense of what our stakeholders wanted and needed from us. But the stocktaking process was not only driven by a feeling of confidence in our tacit self-knowledge, but also by the recognition that DARIAH would be facing a process of moving from five-year to annual financial commitments from members in 2019, as we reached operational stage. The need to have clear and compelling messages for our stakeholders was therefore also in our minds on those January days.

In some ways, it might have made sense for DARIAH to move straight from this dual recognition of needs and opportunities to a full strategic plan. But the progression from tacit knowledge to the words able to capture it is a challenging one, so as an intermediate step, we chose to develop a Strategic Action Plan. This plan, which later became known by its acronym 'STRAPL', gave us a chance to capture the 25 actions we felt most important for the organisation to achieve before the start of its full operational launch. The actions were diverse: from launching a new website to ensuring we integrate EduGain protocols into our network of services, from clarifying roles within the organisation to determining how we might be more proactive in advocating for the arts and humanities and filtering foresight back to these communities.

Perhaps more important than the actions themselves, however, were the processes for community engagement and monitoring that accompanied them. Every level of the DARIAH organisation, from the national contributors to the Working Groups, was made aware of the commitments enshrined in the STRAPL, and encouraged to make their voices heard in refining and improving them. It was only after almost six months in development that the STRAPL was finally accepted officially and launched as a key instrument

of DARIAH policy. After this, however, the hard work began. Ensuring that we kept our commitments at the heart of the organisation was a system on quarterly monitoring meetings to review progress against each of the 25 actions, to prompt where they might be lagging, and to redefine timelines, teams and even action scope as we came to know better what each of them meant for DARIAH. Already in the course of 2017 we were able to see the impact of this taking place, with operational details from hiring decisions to the launch of the new DARIAH Website taking their cues from the STRAPL.

By the end of 2017, a number of STRAPL actions could be considered completed, and many more could not, but what was clear is that our strategy was forming around them. Resource allocation against STRAPL actions became streamlined, with staff roles becoming more clearly aligned to key actions and project funding being sought to deliver some of the most ambitious of our goals. Particularly knotty issues, like knowledge management and communicating a clear DARIAH identity, were able to be pulled and developed for intensive discussion at the 2018 'Strategy Days.' Over the course of 2017, it became clear that our confidence in our ability to do the right things was not unfounded, and, as we move toward the development of a full 7-year strategic plan over the course of 2018, we know that this confidence will serve us, and our stakeholders, very well.

DARIAH STRATEGY DAYS, JANUARY 2017,
CENTRE MARC BLOCH, BERLIN

IV. Looking ahead

As mentioned elsewhere, 2017 felt like the taking of new breath for DARIAH in many ways. January saw the organisation bring on new members of the Board of Directors, a new Chief Integration Officer, a new Chair and Deputy Chair of the National Coordinators Committee, and new members of the Joint Research Committee. The energy brought to the activities of the organisation by the next generation for DARIAH leadership has set us on a course to build on the infrastructure's first decade of development with assurance and confidence.

The year has prepared us to face the challenges inherent in the **shift to operational phase**, allowing us to clarify our mission and contribution as we prepare to approach our members to make a renewed commitment to their participation. In the next year, we will be reaching out, informally and formally, to ensure that our national members are themselves gaining maximum value from their participation in DARIAH, and that we, at the EU coordination level, are doing everything we can to ensure DARIAH has a positive impact on our members, giving them access to the resources they need to deliver excellent arts and humanities scholarship in the digital age.

We also have been preparing throughout 2017 for the shift from being guided by a Strategic Action Plan to a full **Strategic Plan** by the start of 2019. The difference between these two instruments may seem semantic: after all, each enshrines a set of commitments for a period of time, and guides the coordination of organisational resource allocation and activities. But the DARIAH Strategic Plan will also be a document of vision and self-affirmation, designed not only to bring us through the shift to operational phase, but also to guide us in providing unique and measurable value to our members for a period of seven years. This time frame will allow us to be ambitious in our planning, without being naïve about the changes that might take place in our environment. Making such a set of commitments and releasing such a bold programme for development presents a daunting, but exciting, prospect to guide our work in 2018 and beyond.

We look forward as well to delivering, step by step, on some of the most important commitments we have made to our community. 2018 will see the new **in-kind contributions tracker**, developed in the Humanities at Scale project, come online. Ensuring that tools, services, data and knowledge can circulate freely within DARIAH is a key commitment we make, but it is not an easy one to deliver. For this reason, 2018 will also see us make a significant push to progress the vision of the **DARIAH Marketplace**, for which we will seek major ring-fenced funding. As outlined in DARIAH Director Frank Fischer's keynote address at the November 2017 Innovation Forum, "Research in the digital era is a process, and the way we store and work with our data and tools

has to reflect this." DARIAH always planned to provide "a social marketplace for services" (as pointed out in the "Preparing DARIAH" paper from 2011). Seven years later, we face a richer landscape as regards the number of methods, tools, institutions and overall research activities and diversity in the field of Digital Humanities. This brings with it an increased demand for know-how and orientation. The Marketplace is our answer to that situation. It sets out to be an easy-entry place where scholars from the broader SSH domain will find solutions and resources for the digital aspects of their research, even if they don't regard themselves as digital humanists. 'Resources' can be software and tools as well as datasets or APIs, mainly services ready for direct use. 'Solutions' are conceived as complex objects based on a research question, task or story, accompanied by references to further material helping to craft individual workflows. The rationale behind it is to focus on the methodical, dynamic aspects of the research process to enable sharing and re-use not just of resources but workflows and methodologies, to promote Open Methods next to Open Data and Open Source. The crucial difference to other such catalogues or registries of the past is that it will adopt aspects of an app store. Instead of being just a list of links or database of resources, it will contextualise and interrelate tools, services and datasets offered, with screenshots, tutorials and links to training material, user stories, showcases. It will also encompass community features like user feedback, ratings, the integration of other related channels (social media, project websites), allow categorisation according to multiple classification schemes, such as TaDiRAH and NeMO, and contain qualified links to involved actors – persons and institutions, who authored, contributed to, funded or host a given resource ("Talk to a human", as GitHub calls it). Ideally, the Marketplace will also help to identify gaps in the Digital Humanities toolchain.

To counteract obsolescence (a known problem of similar attempts in the past), a strong focus will be put on the curation and quality assurance of the information gathered and on devising a sustainable governance model, including the building of a community around the Marketplace to ensure its durability.

Finally, 2017 has taught us the power of our role as an interface between the traditions of the humanities and the fast-moving worlds of both technology and research policy. As we face into a year that will surely see initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud take form in a way that may or may not respect or integrate our traditions, we know that it is more important than ever that DARIAH fulfill its role as a translator and protective membrane between these cultures, ensuring arts and humanities researchers are heard on the one side, but also that they know to listen out for emerging opportunities on the other.

Appendix I: Administrative, Legal and Financial Details

Who's who in DARIAH

Organisational chart

Body: Board of Directors

Role: The Board of Directors is the executive body of DARIAH ERIC and its legal representative. It is composed of three directors, appointed by the General Assembly. The BoD provides leadership, represents DARIAH, shapes strategy and controls the performance and is responsible for the day-to-day operations, in support by the DARIAH Coordination Office.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH	Affiliation
Laurent Romary	Director	Inria
Jennifer Edmond	Director	Trinity College Dublin
Frank Fischer	Director	Higher School of Economics, Moscow

Body: Scientific Board

Role: The Scientific Board advises DARIAH, via the General Assembly, on specific issues, such as the future research landscape and technological innovation. Its members are arts and humanities researchers with international reputation in the field and therefore significant experience in digitally enabled research methods.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH/Affiliation
Riccardo Pozzo	Chair of the Scientific Board/Università di Verona
Andrew Prescott	University of Glasgow
Roxane Wyns	LIBIS
Jan Rybicki	Jagiellonian University
Sonja de Leeuw	Utrecht University
Patrik Svensson	UCLA
Jane Ohlmeyer	Trinity College, Dublin
Chad Gaffield	University of Ottawa
Francis Prost	University Paris 1-Panthéon Sorbonne/ CNRS/French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
Manfred Thaller	University of Cologne

Body: DARIAH Coordination Office

Role: The daily work of DARIAH-ERIC is undertaken by the DCO; headed by the Chief Executive Officer (CEO), assisted by the Chief Coordination Officer (COO), it is responsible for financial, legal, coordination and communications operations in respect of all the above bodies for the effective running of the ERIC. It has distributed operations and offices in France (Paris), Germany (Berlin and Göttingen) and the Netherlands (The Hague).

People		
Name		Role in DARIAH
	Mike Mertens	Chief Executive Officer
	Suzanne Dumouchel	Program Implementation Officer
	Anne Grésillon	Chief Organisation Officer
	Marco Raciti	European Project Manager
	Arnaud Roi	Finance Officer
	Yoann Moranville	Developer
	Jakob Epler	Communications Officer
	Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer
	Francesca Morselli	Integration Officer
	Femmy Admiraal	Integration Officer

Body: National Coordinators Committee

Role: Each DARIAH Member Country has its own National Coordinator, who oversees DARIAH activities in his or her country on behalf of its national membership consortium. These activities are the setting up of a national road map for the digitally enabled arts and humanities, and coordinating the submission of in-kind contributions, such as the tools, services, software, collections, expertise and researcher networks that are established as a result of implementing the respective national road map. The NCC meets regularly to integrate national DARIAH activities at the European level.

People		
Name	Role in DARIAH/ Country	Affiliation
Toma Tasovac	Chair of the National Coordinators Committee/Serbia	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities
Sally Chambers	Vice Chair of the National Coordinators Committee	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities
Mörth Karlheinz	Austria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, Austrian Academy of Sciences
Christophe Verbruggen	Belgium	Ghent Centre of Digital Humanities, Ghent University
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar	Croatia	Archive, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard	Denmark	Digital Humanities Lab Denmark
Stéphane Pouyllau	France	Huma-Num (CNRS)
Mirjam Blümm	Germany	State and University Library Göttingen
Helen Katsiadakis	Greece	Academy of Athens
Orla Murphy	Ireland	University College Cork
Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Italy	Italian Council of Research
Andreas Fickers	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Henk Wals	Netherlands	International Institute of Social History
Jakub Szprot	Poland	University of Warsaw
Amélia Aguiar de Andrade	Portugal	Infrastructure ROSSIO
Jurij Hadalin	Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History/Primorska University

Body: Joint Research Committee

Role: The JRC organises the integration of DARIAH's technical developments and innovation activities. It is chaired by DARIAH's Chief Integration Officer (CIO) and consists of the Heads of each of DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH	Affiliation
Andrea Scharnhorst, Chair of the JRC	Chief Integration Officer	DARIAH/DANS
Tibor Kálmán, Vice-Chair of the JRC	Heads of VCC1	GWDG
Matej Durco		ACDH-OeAW
Agiatis Benardou	Heads of VCC2	Digital Curation Unit, ATHENA R.C.
Marianne Ping Huang		Aarhus University
Nicolas Larrousse	Heads of VCC3	Huma-Num
Marcin Werla		Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
Fabio Ciotti	Heads of VCC4	University of Roma Tor Vergata
Dirk Wintergrün		Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

Appendix II: Finances

DARIAH ERIC consists of 17 member countries that contribute to its budget in two different ways: through cash contributions and in-kind contributions. In 2017, according to the budget voted by the General Assembly, the contributions from the member countries amount to:

- 2017 Cash contribution: 679 810€
- 2017 In-kind contribution: 4.081.406 €

Resources

Due to their very nature, the in-kind contributions are not included in the calculation of resources available to run DARIAH's operations. The total income 2017 is mostly composed of cash contributions plus some one-time fundings dedicated to the organisation of events, such as the lexical data masterclass organised in December 2017.

DARIAH balance 2016	495 028 €
DARIAH income 2017	729 351 €
DARIAH expenses 2017	729 008 €
Balance 2017	343 €
Total balance	495 371 €

Operating expenses

The largest component of operating expenses is by far the personnel costs which represents 70% of the total costs.

"DARIAH theme" refers to the annual call for projects. The 2017 edition was about "Cultural Heritage and Humanities Research". 7 projects were selected for a total amount of 66.090€, funded partly in 2017.

"WG funding" relates to a specific call for projects addressed to the DARIAH Working Groups. 12 projects were selected for a total amount of 56.509€, funded partly in 2017.

Type of costs	Amount
Personnel Costs	513 049 €
Event Organisation	57 569 €
DARIAH Theme	43 948 €
Travel	40 640 €
Communication	34 442 €
WG Funding	14 800 €
Consumables	6 885 €
Bank Charges	6 095 €
Catering	5 292 €
Hotel	4 241 €
Conference/ Membership Fee	1 016 €
Server Support	829 €
Petty cash	200 €
Total	729 007,68 €

European projects

European projects funding is solely used to carry out specific projects in which DARIAH is involved in:

- Humanities at Scale: Evolving the DARIAH-ERIC (HaS-DARIAH), Grant agreement number 675570
- DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined (DESIR), Grant agreement number 731081
- Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimisation and Synergies (PARTHENOS), Grant agreement number 65419
- High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure (HIRMEOS), Grant agreement number 731102
- The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase (E-RHIS PP), Grant agreement number 739503

	Income	Expenses
HaS-DARIAH	204 879 €	204 879 €
DESIR	14 162 €	14 162 €
PARTHENOS	46 407 €	46 407 €
HIRMEOS	167 €	167 €
E-RHIS PP	2 115 €	2 115 €
Total	267 730 €	267 730 €

Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

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